

CONDENSATIONS OF ARYLDIAZONIUM SALTS WITH REACTIVE UNSATURATED COMPOUNDS. PART VIII. ACTION OF ARYL-DIAZONIUM CHLORIDES WITH β -4-METHOXY- AND β -3:4-DIMETHOXYBENZOYLACRYLIC ACIDS

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Aryldiazonium chlorides afford 4'-methoxy- and 3':4'-dimethoxy chalcones when coupled under Meerwein's conditions with β -4-methoxy- and β -3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acids. The latter two acids seem to undergo reaction more satisfactorily than the parent acid in the Meerwein reaction.

In a previous investigation (Mehra and Mathur, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 465), β -benzoylacrylic acid was allowed to react with various diazonium chlorides having a negative substituent, under Meerwein's conditions (Meerwein *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, ii, 132, 251). It was reported that decarboxylation occurred during the coupling reaction, resulting in the formation of chalcones, thus:

The chalcones could be recovered by extraction of the complex reaction products with aqueous potassium bisulphite or e.g., in the case of the nitrochalcones, with 80-85% sulphuric acid. Yield of chalcone was good in reactions with *p*-chloro- and *p*-nitrobenzenediazonium chlorides and poor with *m*- and *o*-chlorodiazonium compounds. The Meerwein reaction has now been studied with β -4-methoxy- and β -3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acids.

Benzene, *p*- and *o*-chloro-, *p*- and *o*-bromo-, *p*-, *m*- and *o*-nitro-benzenediazonium chlorides have been allowed to react with 4-methoxybenzoylacrylic acid. Benzene, *p*-, *m*- and *o*-nitrobenzenediazonium chlorides have also been allowed to react with 3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acid. In every case decarboxylation occurs during coupling which can be represented in a way analogous to the reaction (I.). The chalcones have been recovered as described in our earlier communication (*loc. cit.*). The products from 4-methoxybenzoylacrylic acid are listed in Table I and those from 3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acid, in Table II. 4-Nitro-, 3-nitro- and 2-nitro-3':4'-dimethoxychalcones are new products. Also, the syntheses of the last three chalcones, needed for comparison, have been recorded for the first time from 4-, 3- and 2-nitrobenzaldehydes and 3:4-dimethoxyacetophenone respectively.

Due to the presence of considerable amount of byproducts, presumably some dimeric forms of the chalcones, in the reaction mixture, a strict evaluation of the reactivity of the methoxybenzoylacrylic acids has not been possible. It is significant, however, to note that benzenediazonium chloride, which is generally less reactive, can couple to furnish 7-8% yield of 4'-methoxy- and 3':4'-dimethoxychalcones.

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4-Methoxy- and 3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acids were prepared by the reaction of anisole and veratrole respectively with maleic anhydride in the presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (vide Dave and Nargund, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, 7, Part III, 191)

Syntheses of 4-Nitro-3-Nitro-, and 2-Nitro-3':4'-dimethoxychalkones.—4-Nitrobenzaldehyde (2 g.) and 3:4-dimethoxyacetophenone (2.6 g.) were dissolved in alcohol (12 c.c.) and then treated with 10 drops NaOH solution (conc.). Crystals of 4-nitro-3':4'-dimethoxychalkone appeared after sometime. These were filtered, washed with alcohol and recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 180° . (Found: C, 64.62; H, 4.95. $C_{17}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 65.2; H, 4.8 per cent). In the same way were prepared 3-nitro-3':4'-dimethoxychalkone, m.p. 128° (Found: C, 65.1; H, 4.7. $C_{17}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 65.2; H, 4.8 per cent) and 2-nitro-3':4'-dimethoxychalkone, m.p. $147-48^\circ$ (from alcohol) (Found: C, 64.5; H, 4.88. $C_{17}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 65.2; H, 4.8 per cent).

Coupling reactions.—The reactions were done as in experiments with benzoylacrylic acid (*loc. cit.*). The amine (M/40), dissolved in 25% HCl (9 c.c.) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (1.90 g.) and the diazotised solution (ca. 20 c.c.) added to a solution of 4-methoxy- or 3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acid (M/40) in acetone (30 c.c.) containing also powdered sodium acetate (8 g.) and copper chloride (1g. in 5 c.c. H_2O). There was brisk effervescence which lasted for 2 to 3 hours. The evolved gases, when led through baryta water, precipitated $BaCO_3$. After keeping overnight, the reaction mixture was steam-distilled, and the green aqueous layer in the distilling flask decanted over. The semisolid mass was digested with cold 2N-alkali. The alkali-insoluble matter was boiled with saturated potassium bisulphite solution (ca. 20 c.c.), cooled, diluted with water (20 c.c.) and filtered. The filtered sulphite liquor was basified with strong aqueous caustic soda (60%). The chalkones were precipitated which were crystallised out from the appropriate solvents.

In the case of the nitrochalkones, the alkali-digested matter was extracted with 85% H_2SO_4 and the acid extract filtered through glass wool over crushed ice. From the benzene solution of the crude nitrochalkones, the tarry matter was separated by precipitation with petroleum ether and filtration. The benzene-petroleum ether solution on concentration yielded products which on further crystallisation from ethanol or methanol furnished the pure nitrochalkones. In the case of 2-nitro-4'-methoxychalkone, however, addition of petroleum ether to the benzene solution of the crude product precipitated the chalkone directly. This was recrystallised from alcohol.

The quantities of the reactants for the coupling reactions (*vide supra*) were adjusted according as M/60 or M/80 quantities of the methoxybenzoylacrylic acids were used.

The semisolid masses, left after digestion with cold 2N-alkali, invariably had a certain amount of ether-insoluble matter. The latter developed a carmine-red colour with H_2SO_4 (conc.), indicating the presence of dimeric forms of chalkones also in the reaction mixture (cf. Stobbe and Breimer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1929, ii, 123, 43).

TABLE I

Interaction of various diazonium chlorides with 4-methoxybenzoylacrylic acid.

Amine diazotised.	NaOH-in sol. matter.	Yield.	X =	Cryst. shape & solvent.	M.P.	
					Found.	Lit
Aniline (M/80)	1.9 g.	0.20 g. 7.0%	H	EtOH; light yellow needles. ¹	106°	105-106°
p-Chloro-aniline (M/40)	5.6	0.91 13.3	4-Cl	Ethyl acetate; slightly yellow plates. ²	130-31°	130-31° ³
o-Chloro-aniline (M/40)	4.9	0.85 12.4	2-Cl	Petroleum ether; yellow plates. ³	92°	91.5-92°
p-Bromo-aniline (M/80)	2.7	0.42 10.3	4-Br	EtOH; yellow flakes. ⁴	153°	152-53°
o-Bromo-aniline (M/80)	2.5	0.37 9.3	2-Br	EtOH; yellow-white needles. ⁵	78°	79.5°
p-Nitro-aniline (M/40)	4.6	1.60 22.6	4-NO ₂	Do; yellow needles. ⁶	169°	169°
m-Nitro-aniline (M/40)	4.9	0.73 10.3	3-NO ₂	Do; light yellow needles. ⁷	153°	152-53°
o-Nitro-aniline (M/80)	1.3	0.60 8.4	2-NO ₂	MeOH; brown-yellow needles. ⁶	111-13°	113°

1. Staudinger and Kon, *Annalen*, 1911, 383, 123. It may be remarked that diazotised aniline affords only traces of chalkone in its reaction with benzoylacrylic acid (unpublished result).
2. Strans and Blankenborn, *ibid*, 1913, 416 254.
3. Pfeiffer *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1928, *ii*, 119, 122.
4. Percy Barnes *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3135.
5. Pfeiffer *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1928, *ii*, 119, 124.
6. Kaufmann, *Ber.*, 1921, 68, 800.
7. Pfeiffer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1925, *ii*, 109, 46.

TABLE II

Interaction of various diazonium chlorides with 3:4-dimethoxybenzoylacrylic acid.

Amine diazotised.	Yield	X =	Cryst. shape & solvent.	M.P. &
				mixed M.P.
Aniline (M/4b)	0.50 g.	8.1%	H	*83-84°
p-Nitroaniline (M/60)	1.10	21.2	4-NO ₂	Alcohol. 179°
m-Nitroaniline (M/60)	1.15	22.1	3-NO ₂	Do 126-27°
o-Nitroaniline (M/60)	1.20	23.1	2-NO ₂	Do 146-47°

* Kaufmann and Kiser (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 3797) record m.p. 85°.

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